

Analysis of Operational and Service Performance on the Loyalty of Sumatran LRT Passengers South in 2022

AZIS OKTA RISDIANA
19C606001047

Department of Transportation Management
Trisakti Institute of Transportation & Logistics
Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- Evaluation of service quality and service quality during passenger satisfaction are determining factors toward passenger loyalty. As such, there are necessary efforts to increase passenger satisfaction. The research was conducted in Station of LRT South Sumatra with sample amounting to 100 employees. Data was gathered through instrument in form with tested. Likert scale The used data analysis method is path analysis. First research result found that service quality has positive and significant correlation towards passenger satisfaction. Therefore, it can be concluded that service quality has positive and significant correlation towards passenger satisfaction. Relevant service quality and service quality in passenger satisfaction has effects to increase passenger loyalty, thus passenger satisfaction as intervening variable is proved to improve service quality and service quality towards passenger loyalty.

Keywords:- Employee coordination, operational performance, productivity of coal loading and unloading equipment (Conveyer), customer satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

The people of Palembang City often face difficulties in carrying out mobility in supporting their daily activities, because public transportation services are limited in providing services to all areas in Palembang city. So that in their daily lives people often rely on the use of private cars, taxis, either regular taxis or online taxis, base motorcycle taxi transportation or online motorcycle taxis. For this reason, the role of mass transportation in Palembang City in serving the transportation community safely, comfortably and affordably with a wide coverage in Palembang city is something urgent to realize.

Light Rail Transit (LRT) South Sumatra, which has 12 stations and 1 depot and a line length of 234 KM, is one of the train-based public transportation that is expected to solve transportation problems in Palembang City. Another mass public transportation that has been operating in Palembang City is currently the Trans Musi BRT Transportation. Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) is a customer-oriented mass transportation system that combines elements of stations, vehicles (buses), planning, and intelligent transportation systems into a unique integrated system.

But unfortunately, during its operation, the South Sumatra Light Rail Transit (LRT) has not become the main

choice for residents of Palembang city and its surroundings in transportation. Therefore, in order for the level of use of South Sumatra Light Rail Transit (LRT) to be more optimal, it is necessary to implement a number of policies and develop a support system to further improve quality because there are still internal problems in order to achieve passenger satisfaction which will cause passenger loyalty in the use of LRT.

The South Sumatra LRT is authorized to increase this in order to create a good state institution goal. Improving operational performance will realize good results and is supported by quality of service in order to increase passenger confidence so as to achieve LRT passenger loyalty.

However, the problem faced by the south Sumatra LRT at this time is, the availability of stations evenly which causes people to still think about traveling using the LRT, and there are still delays in LRT arrival hours at the station, this will have an impact on worker passengers and will reduce public confidence, not to mention inadequate distasuin facilities where what passengers are looking for is comfort at the station either in terms of waiting for LRT arrival or others, then accessibility with other modes of transportation that are not friendly where passengers either disembarking or boarding will use other modes of transportation either to get to the station or after from the station, and plus operational coordination is still not good. Where the above presentation will have an impact on the loyalty of LRT passengers.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEM

This study tries to answer the following questions:

- Is there any direct effect on operational performance on the satisfaction of South Sumatra LRT passengers in 2022?
- Is there any effect on service quality directly affecting the satisfaction of South Sumatra LRT passengers in 2022?
- Is there any effect on operational performance directly affecting the loyalty of South Sumatra LRT passengers in 2022?
- Is there any influence on service quality directly affecting the loyalty of the South Sumatra LRT in 2022?
- Is there an effect of passenger satisfaction directly affecting the loyalty of South Sumatra LRT passengers in 2022?
- Is there an indirect effect of operational performance on passenger loyalty through the satisfaction of South Sumatra LRT passengers in 2022?

- Is there an indirect influence of passenger quality on passenger loyalty through the satisfaction of South Sumatra LRT passengers in 2022?

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Operation Performance

According (hasan et al. , 2017) Company performance is the result of a management activity on a company. Of the results of such performances passed as a measuring parameter in judging a success of the company's own management, Company performances are not uniquely exerted from internal processing control. The more small companies, Great even medium and flourishing. Some companies are very intense monitoring how the performance progress of a company is also the division of duty and responsibility, The company's performance is something produced by the company within a certain period and refers to the set standard. Company performance mills can be measured by financial and non-finance measures. Non-finance performance measures include customer satisfaction, The productivity and cost effectivity.

According to (adham, was a literary 2019) operational sense an abstracting nature to ease the measurement of a variable. Or operational can be defined as a guide to do an activity or research work. According to characteristics diobservasi operational definition to be defined or change konsep- concept of konstruk with who described a behavior or the symptoms are observed, tested and determined the truth to others.

In the journal excerpt (Ananto, 2016) operational performance comes from the word performance (performance). As stated by Mangkunegara (2009) that the term operational performance comes from the word job performance or actual performance (work performance or actual achievements achieved by a person) namely the results of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. So according to Mangkunegara (2009), work performance or achievement is the result of quality and quantity work achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

According to explanation of operational performance is a job given to a person in performing tasks at the base of speed, experience, and time then that result can be measured because the performance of operandioal results from several dimensions that have, the purpose of the organization, correcting process, and also quality initiatives measured variables both numbers and certain attributes.

B. Quality Service

According to (Waluyo, 2018) Quality is the extent to which the product meets its specifications, service quality is the performance of a product or service that can meet customer needs or even exceed customer expectations not just one use but repeatedly so as to provide satisfaction, then the customer perception obtained from the product or service has quality.

According to (Fandi, 2011) customer value includes not only quality, but also a price. A certain service may have superior quality, but it is evaluated as low-value because the price is too expensive. As well as customer satisfaction and service quality, the concept of customer value is still in the development stage. One of the measures developed to evaluate customer value is Perval (Perceived Value). In addition, customer value measurement can also be based on three main roles of customers in purchasing decisions, namely user values, buyer values, and payer values.

According to Hanif Mauludin (2004) in the journal citation (Winoto et al., 2016) defines service quality as a result of perception and comparison between customer expectations and actual service performance. According to Parasuraman, there are 2 main factors that affect the quality of services, namely expected service and perceived service

The author explains from some of the explanations above that the quality of service is based on the understandings above, it can be concluded that the quality of service is the actions and abilities of employees in a company that are carried out with full commitment to provide the best and quality service to consumers, fellow employees, and company leaders.

C. Passenger Satisfaction

According to Drucker Nasution (2004:104) in Darwin Lie, et al(2017), saying that for the customer, what a company produces is not so important thinking about what it buys. This means we have to give them what they really want, when and how they get it. According to Umar (2005 : 65) in Dede (2017) states that consumer satisfaction is the level of consumer feeling after comparing between what he receives and his expectations. Consumer satisfaction plays an important and critical role for the continuity and development of a company's life. By listening to consumers then responding to wishes or requests, it will provide more satisfactory results and make consumers loyal.

By (fandi, 2011) customer value does not only include quality, It's also a price..A certain service could have superior qualities., But evaluated is low because it's overpriced..As well as customer satisfaction and quality service, concept customer value is still in progress. One of the sizes developed for evaluating customer value is perval (perceived value). Other than that., customer value measurement may also be based on the top three customer roles in the purchase decision, It's user values., buy Values, and payer values.

In the journal excerpt (ratnasari), 2015 customer comforts are the level of one's feelings as a result of the comparison between reality and hope received from products and services that get far less work than the customer expected, The buyer is not satisfied if performance meets expectations or exceeds expectations, The buyer is content or very happy. The customer generally expects products in the form of goods or services consumed to be accepted and enjoyed in good and satisfying service.

The author explains from some of the explanations above on passenger satisfaction, namely, Satisfaction is a

response from passengers to the evaluation of the discrepancies felt between previous expectations and the performance they have felt. The level of passenger satisfaction is the function of the difference between visible performance and hope.

D. Passenger Loyalty

According to Griffin in Sangadji and Sopiah (2013:104) states "loyalty is defined as non random purchase expressed over time by some decision making unit." Based on the definition, it can be explained that loyalty refers more to the behavioral form of decision-making units to make continuous purchases of goods or services of a selected company.

According to (Ramadhan, 2020) customer loyalty is the willingness of customers to use the company's services in the long term.

According to Suwondo & Marjan (2017) customer loyalty is defined as a good image of the customer towards the company, responsible for buying back the company's products or services and trustworthy product or service to others.

According to Siagian & Cahyono (2014) customer loyalty is one of the very meaningful results of an online business. Meanwhile, according to Normasari (2013) customer loyalty is an asset and has a meaningful position in an industry.

According to (Maheswari & Aksari, 2019) customer loyalty is a measure that can be done to predict sales and financial growth. Loyal consumers will usually recommend the products and services used to the closest people, besides customers who are already compatible with the services and products offered are rare to change places or brands.

Based on the explanation above, the author makes a synthesis that Customer Loyalty is a customer attitude or behavior in committing to service users to decide whether to reuse the service.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

According to (Sugiyono, 2019) Non Probability Sampling is a technique that does not provide equal opportunities for each element or member of the population to be selected as a sample. The Non Probability Sampling technique chosen is by saturated sampling (census), which is a sampling method when all members of the population are used as samples. This is often done when the population is small, less than 30 people.

In this study, the samples that will be taken are all Employees of the South Sumatra LRT Station during a field survey at the Station and the South Sumatra LRT collectors as users of LRT transportation services, namely 100 people. The saturated sample method is a sample determination technique when all members of the population are used to be sampled.

V. RESULT

A. Validity Test

The critical limit value of validity is 0.1966. If the correlation or r value is less than or less than 0.1966 then the questionnaire item is declared invalid. Conversely, if the calculated value of r is greater than 0.1966 then the questionnaire item is declared valid.

The following are the results of the validity test of the research instrument (questionnaire) for each of the variables studied:

Table 1: Validity Test Result

Pernyataan	Nilai Koefisien Koreksi (r hitung)				Status
	(X1)	(X2)	(Y)	(Z)	
No. 1	0.787	0.786	0.786	0.786	Valid
No. 2	0.782	0.777	0.781	0.786	Valid
No. 3	0.606	0.605	0.598	0.610	Valid
No. 4	0.779	0.773	0.778	0.767	Valid
No. 5	0.920	0.914	0.919	0.919	Valid
No. 6	0.720	0.709	0.708	0.725	Valid

Source: primary data, processed by the statistical package for the 25th version of social science.

Table 1 shows that each item of each of the variable questions of Operational Performance (X1), Quality of Service (X2), Passenger Satisfaction (Y) and Passenger Loyalty (Z) is all declared valid.

B. Reliability Test

Table 2: Reliability Test Result

Variable	Nilai Alpha	Nilai Batas	Status
Kinerja Operasional (X1)	0.860	0.70	Reliable
Kualitas Pelayanan (X2)	0.855	0.70	Reliable
Kepuasan Penumpang (Y)	0.856	0.70	Reliable
Loyalitas Penumpang (Z)	0.859	0.70	Reliable

Source: primary data, processed by the statistical package for the 25th version of social science.

Table 2 shows that the entire alpha value item in each variable is reliable, Because kronbach's alpha coefficient is greater than 0.70.

Of the validity and reliable results of the analysis mentioned above, The total statement points of each variable can be used and distributed to the entire respondents (100 respondents). Because each item shows legitimate and reliable results, Further research can be done.

C. Partial Test

Table 3: Partial Test Structure 1

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.642	2.396		2.355	.021
	KinerjaOperasional	.399	.096	.382	4.155	.000
	KualitasPelayanan	.367	.117	.289	3.144	.002

a. Dependent Variable: KepuasanPenumpang

Source: primary data, processed by the statistical package for the 25th version of social science.

- Operational Performance (X1) affects Passenger Satisfaction(Y). Showing the test results individually (partial) / t test sig 0.000 less than 0.05 or $[0.000 < 0.05]$, Then the coefficient way is more analysis. That's why, Positive operational performance and significant impact on passenger satisfaction. The immediate impact of operational performance on the satisfaction shown by a beta is 0.382 or 38.2 %.
- Service Quality (X2) affects Passenger Satisfaction(Y). Showing the individual (partial) test / t test obtained a Sig value of 0.002 less than 0.05 or $[0.001 < 0.05]$, then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, the Quality of Service has a positive and significant effect on Passenger Satisfaction. The magnitude of the effect of Service Quality on Passenger Satisfaction is indicated by a Beta value of 0.289 or 28.9 percent.

Table 4: Partial Test Structure 2

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.122	1.572		.714	.477
	KinerjaOperasional	.379	.067	.394	5.692	.000
	KualitasPelayanan	.311	.078	.266	3.978	.000
	KepuasanPenumpang	.334	.065	.363	5.161	.000

a. Dependent Variable: LoyalitasPenumpang

Source: primary data, processed by the statistical package for the 25th version of social science.

- Operational Performance (X1) affects Passenger Loyalty (Z). Showing the individual (partial) test / t test obtained a Sig value of 0.000 less than 0.05 or $[0.000 < 0.05]$, then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, Operational Performance has a positive and significant effect on Passenger Loyalty. The amount of direct effect of Operational Performance on Passenger Loyalty is indicated by a Beta value of 0.394 or 39.4 percent.
- Quality of Service (X2) affects Passenger Loyalty (Z) Showing the individual test (partial) / t test obtained Sig 0.000 less than 0.05 or $[0.000 < 0.05]$, then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, the Quality of Service has a positive and significant effect on Passenger Loyalty. The magnitude of the effect of Service Quality on Passenger Loyalty is indicated by a Beta value of 0.266 or 26.6 percent.
- Passenger Satisfaction (Y) affects Passenger Loyalty (Z). Showing the test individually (partial) / t test obtained a value of Sig value of 0.000 less than 0.05 or $[0.000 < 0.05]$, then the coefficient of path analysis is significant. With the dynamic, Passenger Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Passenger Loyalty. The magnitude of the effect of Passenger Satisfaction on Passenger Loyalty is indicated by a Beta value of 0.363 or 36.3 percent.

D. Sobel Test

Sobel tests are tests to see if relationships through mediation variables can significantly function as mediators in relationships. To make it easier to calculate the z's value of the sobel test, You can take advantage of online danielsooper application through the www.danielsooper.com with the menu Statistic Calculator→Mediation Models → Sobel Test Calculator for Significance of Mediation, with the following results:

- Mediation Test the Effect of Operation Performance on Passenger Loyalty through Passenger Satisfaction.

Fig. 1: Sobel test model 1

Based on Figure 1 shows a one-tailed probability of $0.00007133 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the Passenger Satisfaction variable can function as a mediator or be able to mediate the indirect influence of Operation Performance on Passenger Loyalty.

- Mediation Test the Effect of Service Quality on Passenger Loyalty through Passenger Satisfaction.

Fig. 2: Sobel test model 2

Based on Figure 2, shows a one-tailed probability of $0.00081613 < 0.05$, so that it can be concluded that the Passenger Satisfaction variable can function as a mediator or be able to mediate the indirect influence of Service Quality on Passenger Loyalty.

E. Goodness of Fittest Test

Table 6: R Square Sub Structure 1

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.568 ^a	.322	.308	1.086

a. Predictors: (Constant), KualitasPelayanan, KinerjaOperasional

Source: primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25

Table 7: R Square Sub Structure 2

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.823 ^a	.677	.667	.693

a. Predictors: (Constant), KepuasanPenumpang, KualitasPelayanan, KinerjaOperasional

Source: primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 25

Then the total diversity of data that can explain by the model is measured by:

$$R^2_m = 1 - (1 - R^2_1) \cdot (1 - R^2_2) \cdot (1 - R^2_p) \quad (1)$$

$$R^2_m = 1 - (1 - R^2_1) \cdot (1 - R^2_2) \cdot (1 - R^2_p) \cdot R^2_m \quad (2)$$

$$= 1 - (0.322) \times (0.677) \quad (3)$$

$$R^2_m = 0.782$$

The R^2_m value of 0.782 means that the diversity of data that can be described by the model is 78.20 percent, while the remaining 21.80 percent is explained by other variables outside the model. Thus the research model has a high predictive ability over the behavior of dependent variables characterized by a high coefficient of determination above 50 percent.

VI. DISCUSSION

- **H1**, Operational performance has a positive and significant effect on passenger satisfaction. Based on analysis results, coefficient from operational performance variable path to passenger satisfaction variable acquired at 0.382 or 38.2 percent by 0, This means that the better operational performance, Passenger satisfaction will increase. That way passenger satisfaction obtained by passengers will increase, this will have a good impact on the South Sumatra LRT and will increase public confidence in the use of public transportation, especially the South Sumatra LRT.
- **H2**, The quality of services has positive effects and significant at satisfaction penumpang. berdasarkan analisis, the coefficient of the quality of service to a variable satisfaction passengers obtained at 0.289 or 28.9 by importance 0.002. ini means that the better the quality of services, more passengers will be more satisfaction. That way passenger satisfaction obtained by passengers will increase, this will have a good impact on the South Sumatra LRT and will increase public confidence in the use of public transportation, especially the South Sumatra LRT.
- **H3**, Operational performance has a positive and significant effect on loyalty passengers analysis, the coefficient of operational performance the variable variable allegiance to the passengers were obtained at 0.394 or 0.000. hal 39.4 percent on the importance of the better operational performance, better passengers will loyalty. That way passenger loyalty will increase, this will have a good impact on the south Sumatra LRT and will increase public confidence in the use of public transportation, especially the south Sumatra LRT.
- **H4**, Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Passenger Loyalty. Based on the results of the analysis, the coefficient of the Service Quality variable path to the Passenger Loyalty variable was obtained at 0.266 or 26.6 percent with a significance of 0.000. This means that the better the Quality of Service, the better the Passenger Loyalty will be. That way passenger loyalty will increase, this will have a good impact on the south Sumatra LRT and

will increase public confidence in the use of public transportation, especially the south Sumatra LRT.

- **H5**, Passenger Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Passenger Loyalty. Based on the results of the analysis, the coefficient of the passenger satisfaction variable path to the Passenger Loyalty variable was obtained at 0.363 or 36.3 percent with a significance of 0.000. This means that the better the Passenger Satisfaction, the better the Passenger Loyalty will be. That way Passenger Loyalty can be achieved properly, this will have a good impact on the South Sumatra LRT and will increase public confidence in the use of public transportation, especially the south Sumatra LRT.
- **H6**, Passenger Satisfaction is able to function as a mediator or mediate the effect of Operational Performance on Passenger Loyalty. This means that appropriate Passenger Satisfaction with the operational performance applied is able to increase Passenger Loyalty, So the passengers intervened with the satisfaction variables that indeed proved to serve to amplify the effect of operational performance on the passengers' loyalty, This will have an effect on good publishing south lrt sumatra and will provide additional with public confidence in the use of public transportation, Especially south sumatra LRT
- **H7**, Passenger Satisfaction is able to function as a mediator or mediate the influence of Service Quality on Passenger Loyalty. This means that appropriate Passenger Satisfaction with the Quality of Service applied is able to increase Passenger Loyalty so that Passenger Satisfaction as an intervening variable is proven to serve to strengthen the influence of Service Quality on Passenger Loyalty, this will have a good impact on the South Sumatra LRT and will increase public confidence in the use of public transportation, especially the South Sumatra LRT.

VII. CONCLUSION

From the results of research and overall analysis, some conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- Operational Performance has a positive and significant effect on Passenger Satisfaction.
- Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Passenger Satisfaction.
- Operational Performance has a positive and significant effect on Passenger Loyalty.
- Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Passenger Loyalty.
- Passenger Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Passenger Loyalty.
- Passenger satisfaction can serve as a mediator or mediate indirect effects of operational performance on passenger loyalty.
- Passenger satisfaction may serve as a mediator or may not directly mediate the influence of quality service on the passengers of loyalty.

VIII. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the conclusions above, the authors provide suggestions and recommendations as follows:

- To increase and maintain Passenger Loyalty and to avoid decreasing sumatra lrt users or passengers
- South caused by passenger dissatisfaction which results in not reusing South Sumatra LRT services, it is necessary to improve operational performance and service quality to increase passenger satisfaction, such as additional operating hours, improved coordination between divisions, procurement of training every 6 months or certification on services, procurement of facilities and infrastructure for passenger comfort, and others. This can lead to an increase in passenger loyalty as service users.
- Other researchers are going to be doing operational performance research, Service Quality, Passenger Satisfaction and Passenger Loyalty are advised to examine other variables including Motivation, work environment, and effectiveness of work also has influence signifikan. sehingga it is expected that this research could be useful in providing input and recommendations to the operator LRT south sumatra and the academic world.

IX. IMPLICATION

Based on the conclusion of the results of research and recommendations that have been described above, The implications are the operational performance and quality of passenger satisfaction services are getting better, The services provided are more in accordance with the customer's expectations, Operational activity can run optimal and in accordance with corporate goals guided by corporate operating standards, The use of technology that is getting easier and easier to access customers online with operational performance and improved quality of service, Any problem that arises will soon find a solution to avoiding passenger disloyalty to reuse services of course with the policy of competent employees, As well as the supply of good facilities and infrastructure from south sumatra lrt to strengthen customer loyalty.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Adham, M. (2019). Upaya Meningkatkan Kinerja Pelaksanaan Operasional Terminal Peti Kemas Pt Pelindo Iv Makassar. *Jurnal Maritim*, 10(1), 21–35. <http://e-journal.polnes.ac.id/index.php/maritim/article/view/422>
- [2.] Ananto, R. (2016). ANALISIS PENGARUH GAYA KEPEMIMPINAN, MOTIVASI DAN DISIPLIN KERJA TERHADAP KINERJA PEGAWAI (Studi Empiris Pada PT DHL Global Forwarding Semarang Branch). *Akuntansi*, 1–73.
- [3.] Fandi. (2011). The Influence of the Store Environment on Quality Inferences and Store Image. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 6(11), 951–952., 8–42.
- [4.] Fauzi, A. A. (2018). Electronic Service Quality on Mobile Application of Online Transportation Services. *Jurnal Manajemen Indonesia*, 18(1), 13–27. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jmi.v18i1.1256>
- [5.] Hasan, H., Darmiasih, I. M. I., & Setyawati, A. (2017). Standar Kinerja Operasional Terminal Mustika Alam Lestari Di Pelabuhan Tanjung Priok. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis Transportasi Dan Logistik*, September 2017, 4(01), 127–134.
- [6.] Mardalena, T., & Asmarita, D. (2020). Pengaruh Pengawasan Bongkar Muat Barang Terhadap Kinerja Operasional. *Jurnal Industri Kreatif (JIK)*, 3(02), 113–125. <https://doi.org/10.36352/jik.v3i02.28>
- [7.] Pribadi, S., Ayudya, A., & Wulandari, R. S. (2017). Pemanfaatan Forklift Untuk Kelancaran Operasional Di Gudang Produsen Susu Kental Manis. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis Transportasi Dan Logistik*, 3(3), 325–328.
- [8.] Ramadhan, M. A. F. (2020). Pengaruh Citra Merek, Kepercayaan, Dan Komitmen Terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan Aplikasi Transportasi Online Gojek Di Kota Malang. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen (JIMMU)*, 4(2), 153. <https://doi.org/10.33474/manajemen.v4i2.3733>
- [9.] Ratnasari, S. (2015). Pengaruh Kualitas Layanan Dan Nilai Pelanggan Terhadap Kepuasan Serta Dampaknya Pada Kepercayaan Pelanggan Pt. Mitra Intertrans Forwarding Cabang Palu. *Katalogis*, 3(1), 116–120.
- [10.] Subekti, S. (2019). Pengaruh Kualitas Layanan dan Nilai Pelanggan Terhadap Loyalitas Penumpang Garuda Indonesia di Bandar Udara Radin Inten II Lampung. *Warta Penelitian Perhubungan*, 31(2), 93–104. <https://doi.org/10.25104/warlit.v31i2.1271>
- [11.] Waluyo, M. R. (2018). Analisis Model Hubungan Kepuasan Dan Loyalitas Pelanggan Transportasi Online. *Tekmapro : Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 13(2), 41–48. <https://doi.org/10.33005/tekmapro.v13i2.41>
- [12.] Winoto, P., Fathoni, A., & Haryono, A. T. (2016). Pengaruh Retailer Performance , Sales Force , Dan Servis Quality Terhadap Customer Trust Dengan Word of Mouth (Wom) Sebagai Variabel Intervening Di Pt H3I Indonesia. *Journal of Management*, 2(2), 110. <http://jurnal.unpand.ac.id/index.php/MS/article/view/496/482> *Engineering and Management*, 13(2), 41–48. <https://doi.org/10.33005/tekmapro.v13i2.41>
- [13.] Winoto, P., Fathoni, A., & Haryono, A. T. (2016). The Effect of Retailer Performance, Sales Force, And Service Quality On Customer Trust With Word of Mouth (Wom) As An Intervening Variable In Pt H3I Indonesia. *Journal of Management*, 2(2), 110. <http://jurnal.unpand.ac.id/index.php/MS/article/view/496/482>